

INFLUENCE OF GENDER AND MARITAL STATUS ON OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND JOB DISSATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined how gender and marital status influences the occupational stress and job dissatisfaction among secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State of Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and their corresponding null hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 level of statistical significance. The exposé-facto research design was adopted for the study with a sample of 382 teachers that were drawn using stratified and convenience sampling techniques. The two instruments used for data collection, Teachers Occupational Stress Assessment Scale (TOSAS) and Teachers' Dissatisfaction Scale (TDAS), were properly validated by experts. Reliability using Cronbach Alpha Method showed that the TOSAS had reliability coefficient of 0.744, while TDAS had a coefficient of 0.716. Data analysis was done using summated mean and standard deviation for the research questions, and two-way ANOVA for the hypotheses. Result showed that gender and marital status had significant influence on the stress level of teachers, as well as their perceived job dissatisfaction. On the basis of the result, it was recommended that teachers should be helped to map out strategies to deal with stressors, especially those arising from students' behavioural problems.

Keywords: Gender, Marital Status, Occupational Stress, Job Satisfaction, Secondary School Teachers etc.

INTRODUCTION

The central role that work plays in the life of humans has received considerable attention from scholars in the field of social sciences generally and from those in organizational studies. In the opinion of Claude (2005), work is the primary condition for the existence of man, in the absence of which survival becomes difficult and even impossible. Supporting this position are Landy and Conte (2004) who asserted that for the current period of human development, 70% of all man's time is dedicated toward career development in the workplace. These positive effects of work notwithstanding, other effects of work have been shown to be inimical to the development of man, especially in the area of mental health. These include aspects like job dissatisfaction, burnout,

occupational stress, chronic pain and social anxiety: Among these negative factors, one that has featured prominently in the literature has been occupational health.

It is worthy to note that the issue of occupational stress is one of the dominant health threats confronting many employees and organisations within the modern workplace. Occupational stress or strain occurs when there are discrepancies between the demands of the workplace and those of the individual (Tsutsumi, 2009). Perhaps, this is the reason why Kyriacou (2001) views occupational stress as the experience of negative emotional states such as frustration, worry, anxiety and depression attributed to work related factors. In this study, occupational stress refers to the pressure one experiences as a result of work. Job stress can result in employee burnout, absenteeism, low morale, ill-health, reduced efficiency and performance (Hannigan, Edwards & Burnard, 2004), When a person feels insufficient in dealing with the demands and challenges of the workplace, he or she experiences stress.

The commitment and effectiveness of teachers is significantly dependent on motivation, morale and job satisfaction. More importantly, teachers are positioned strategically to provide enabling conditions that promote a healthy formal education in any society and as such, when faced with conditions that lead to their dissatisfaction and by extension reduces their maximum devotion to the teaching profession, the standard and quality of education becomes largely undermined. In Nigeria, the teaching profession is replete with teachers who lack job satisfaction, career and organisational commitment (Salami, 2005). Consequently, high turnover has become commonplace among teachers in Nigeria due to poor salary scheme, deplorable working conditions, low prospects, motivation and prestige. Teachers work under immense pressure because their classes are over populated with students who study in dilapidated structures. Adesoje (2004) and Salami (2005) support the statement above when they point to the fact that Nigerian teachers work under extreme stressful conditions. It is pertinent to also mention that a teacher performs other duties together with his/her traditional function of teaching, For example, the teacher has the responsibility of alerting the parents of students whenever such students have learning difficulties; he/she supervises the students' extracurricular activities, acts as loco parents to the students in his care, etcetera. These extra functions that teachers perform are very demanding and all of these dovetails to exacerbate stress level associated with the teaching profession.

In support of the above position, Salami, Salim, Nasir, Arip and Mustafa (2012) opine that the situation has forced teachers into hectic and busy schedules with adverse consequences such as: high levels of stress, unhappiness and job dissatisfaction in recent times. This study explains job dissatisfaction as a worker's expression of displeasure, exasperation, discontent, dislike and disappointments towards his or her work. Job dissatisfaction has been highlighted in various literatures as a contributory to the lack of commitment and high level of absenteeism among teachers. Teachers job dissatisfaction arises when the physical and psychological benefits that accrue from the teacher's job fall below his or her expectation. Siegel and Lane (1982) also state vividly that, job dissatisfaction happens when a teacher derives negative or un-pleasurable emotional response from his or her subjective appraisal of his or her current job situation.

The negative consequences of job dissatisfaction arising from occupational stress among teachers are better left to the imagination. As scholars have shown, this has contributed to low job performance as well as productivity. This has negatively affected the outputs of schools as well as students' achievements while contradicting the axiom that says "every employee has the right to enjoy his/her job as they judiciously carry out their duties daily and retire home with eagerness to return back to work the next day" (Landy & Conte, 2004). This assertion is not the case with teachers considering the fact that they are key players in the achievement of educational goals which are central to the development of any country. Public and private secondary school teachers have different experience in terms of academic performance, salary ratio, working environment and other fringe benefits. According to Okeke (2008), teachers work in stressful environmental conditions. This is likely more the case for those in Bayelsa State where they teach in cult infested school and rife with sea pirates activities. This puts them in a situation where physical attack is all too common. This when added to the large number of students only increases the tendency for job dissatisfaction. Sadly, such situations make such teachers resort to truancy, absenteeism and self-gratification, with the attendant decrease in educational standard and students' performance.

Despite these appalling situations, not all teachers display similar level of job dissatisfaction resulting from occupational stress. This is because while they work in the same environmental conditions, some factors have been implicated that moderate relationship between occupational stress and job dissatisfaction. Two of such factors were investigated in the present studies which are gender and marital status. Demands from social roles and cultural expectations, often determine peoples' behaviour and activities in all facets of life including work situation. As such, one of the basic assumptions of modern life is that male and male female workers do not address situations in their personal professional lives in the same manner. In the vein, it can be relatively agreed that marital status brings on new roles and expectations that guides social behaviour and emotions (Galanakis, Stalikas, Kallia, Karagianni, & Karela, 2009). It was from this perspective, that this study investigated the extent to which the relationship between occupational stress and job dissatisfaction among teachers are influenced by gender and marital status in Bayelsa State secondary schools.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For the theoretical framework of this study, we'll describe in short three major scientific models of work stress: the person-environment, the demand-support-control, and the cognitive behavioural approach. However, we shall be adopting the cognitive behavioural approach which best explain how gender and marital status affects stress levels.

The Person-Environment Fit Theory

In person-environment fit theory, stress results neither from the person, nor from the environment, but from the degree of fit between the two (Spielberger et al., 2001). Stress may occur when the coping supplies do not match the person's needs, or, in some situations, when the coping supplies exceed the person's needs (Devereux, Hastings, & Noone, 2009). Similarly, stress occurs when the

demands of the job exceed the person's capacities but it also may occur in some situations where the abilities exceed the demands. In person-environment fit theory, if the fit between the person and the environment is less complete, individuals may experience workplace stress (Spielberger et al., 2001),

Demand-Control-Support Model

The demand-control-support model (Karasek & Theorell, 1990) states that the generation of occupational stress is affected by the interaction between the perceptions of a person on the work demands, its control on the situation, and the support received. The demand-control-support model states that jobs that are high in demands, low in control and low in social support are those that exhibit the highest risk of stress for people.

The Cognitive-Behavioural Approach

In the cognitive-behavioural approach, stress is conceptualized as a cognitive process (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Within this cognitive-behavioural model, stress is the result of the interaction between the person and its work, this interaction is called "transaction". A stimulus becomes a stressor if it is perceived and interpreted as such (Lazarus, 1995). This model is able to explain individual differences in the stress response elicited from people who are in similar situations or are in a same situation at different times. By implication, women and men according to this theory are expected to experience stress in the work place differently. Similarly, marital status of workers might also be a factor to explain different stress level in the work place.

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

The ex-post facto research design was adopted as the research design for the present study. This design was adopted because the researcher did not manipulate any of the variables in the study such as gender, marital status, occupational stress and job dissatisfaction. The study was conducted in Bayelsa State, one of the states located in the Southern part of Nigeria. It is situated in the core Niger Delta region, between Delta and Rivers States. The population for the study was made up of 8,605 secondary school teachers, while a sample of 382 was used as the sample for the study. The sample was gotten using stratified and convenience sampling techniques from the eight local government areas in the state.

Data for the study was collected using the Teachers Occupational Stress Assessment Scale (TOSAS) and Teachers' Dissatisfaction Scale (TDAS). The TOSAS was designed determine the extent to which teachers experienced stress. It was made up of two sections, A and B. Section A elicited information on the personal data of the teachers such as gender, and marital status. Then section B elicited information on the level of stress among teachers: it is made of 20 items structured in 4-point Likert format. The response scales on the items were: strongly agree (SA), agree (A), Disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). They were weighted 4 points, 3 points, 2 points and 1 point. respectively. Thus, the scale provided a minimum of 10 marks and a maximum of 80 marks.

The second instrument elicited information on the level of teachers' dissatisfaction. It is made up of 20 items that were also structured in Likert format. Just like the first instrument, the response scale were: strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and then strongly disagree (SA). They were also weighted 4 points, 3 points, 2 points and 1 point, respectively. On this note the scale provided a minimum of 10 marks and a maximum of 80 marks.

The validity of the instrument was assessed using the expert panel approach by giving experts in industrial relations to assess the instrument in terms of grammar, suitability to the objectives of the study and their brevity. Reliability was done using the Cronbach Alpha technique by administering the instrument on 30 teachers who were not part of the selected sample for the study. Thereafter alpha coefficients obtained for the two instruments are 0.744 and 0.716 for TOSAS and TDAS respectively. These coefficients obtained indicated that the two instruments are adequately reliable for use for the study. The direct delivery approach was used to collect data from the teachers. The researcher and trained research assistants provided instructions and monitored the filling of the instruments. The instruments were retrieved on the spot after filling. The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis of summated mean for answering the research questions, while two-way ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

To answer the research questions and the corresponding null hypotheses, teachers were first divided into mild, moderate and high stress levels with respect to their gender. The classification was the basis for the range of scores. Hence, teachers who fall into the category of 20-40 marks, were assigned to mild stress level, 41-60 marks were assigned to the moderate stress level group, while the range of 61-80 marks were assigned to the high stress level group.

Research Question One: How do gender differentials in occupational stress influence job dissatisfaction among secondary school teachers?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on the influence of occupational stress on job dissatisfaction of teachers based on their gender

Stress Level	Gender	N	Mean	SD
Mild	Male	25	43.92	11.57
	Female	40	39.73	11.66
	Total	65	41.34	11.70
Moderate	Male	99	46.71	13.61
	Female	152	42.11	9.55
	Total	251	43.92	11.52
High	Male	47	52.72	12.79
	Female	16	45.00	8.22
	Total	63	50.76	12.21

Total	Male	171	47.95	13.39
	Female	208	41.87	9.34
	Total	379	44.61	11.99

In Table 1, it is shown that the mean scores of male and female teachers in the mild stress level are 43.92 and 39.73 respectively. On the other hand, the standard deviation of their scores is 11.57 and 11.66 respectively. Hence the male teachers experience a higher level of job dissatisfaction than their female counterparts. For the moderate stress level, the mean scores of the male and female teachers are 46.71 and 42.11 respectively. The standard deviation of their scores is 13.61 and 9.55 respectively. Thus, the male teachers also experience a higher level of job dissatisfaction than their female counterparts. Then for the high stress level, the male teachers had the mean score of 52.76 job dissatisfaction while the females had the mean score of 45.00. The standard deviation of their scores is 12.79 and 8.22 for male and female teachers respectively. Their mean scores indicate that the male teachers experienced job dissatisfaction more than their female counterparts. Furthermore, from a general perspective and irrespective of the teacher's stress levels, the male teachers had the mean score of 47.95 (SD = 13.39) while the female had the mean score of 41.87 (SD 9.34). Hence it is deduced that the male teachers irrespective of their stress level experienced job dissatisfaction more than their female counterparts.

Hypothesis One: The influence of occupational stress on the male and female teachers' job dissatisfaction do not differ significantly.

Table 2: Summary of two-way analysis of variance on the influence of the occupational stress on job dissatisfaction

Source of Variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean	F	P-value
Stress Level	1350.36	2	675.18	5.15	0.006
Gender	1649.48	1	1649.48	12.57	0.000
Stress Level x gender	107.85	2	53.92	0.411	0.663
Error	48932.04	373	131.19		
Total	54383.76	378			

From Table 2 it can easily be seen that the f-ratio obtained for stress level is 5.15 at the df of 2 and 373 at 0.000 level ($P < 0.05$). This indicates a significant influence of stress level on teacher's job dissatisfaction in table 2, it is also shown that the calculated f-ratio obtained for gender is 12.57 at df of 1 and 373 at 0.006 level of significance ($P < 0.05$). Thus, gender significantly influences the job dissatisfaction of teachers. Additionally, table 2 shows that the f-ratio obtained for the interaction effect between stress and gender is at the df of 2 and 373 at 0.663 level of significance ($P > 0.05$). Thus, interaction effect between stress level and gender do not significantly influence teachers' job dissatisfaction.

Research Question Two: How does occupational stress influence teachers' job dissatisfaction based on their marital status?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the influence of occupational stress levels on teacher's job dissatisfaction based on their marital status.

Stress Level	Marital Status	N	Mean	SD
Mild	Single	9	40.22	9.77
	Married	29	38.72	9.23
	Divorced	19	38.16	11.30
	Widowed	8	59.63	5.76
	Total	65	41.34	11.70
Moderate	0-5 yrs	48	43.33	10.28
	Single	153	43.69	10.06
	Married	23	37.39	13.64
	Divorced	27	51.81	15.24
	Total	251	43.92	11.52
High	Single	11	48.18	11.75
	Married	34	47.74	10.94
	Divorced	9	59.78	7.84
	Widowed	9	56.33	15.92
	Total	63	50.76	12.21
Total	Single	68	43.71	10.54
	Married	216	43.66	10.34
	Divorced	51	41.63	14.48
	Widowed	44	54.16	14.25
	Total	379	44.61	11.99

A critical look at Table 3 revealed that for the mild stress level the single teachers had a mean score of 40.22, married ones had the mean score of 38.72, those divorced among them had the mean score of 38.16, while the widowed had the mean score of 59.63. Their mean scores indicated that widows had the highest level of dissatisfaction in the job followed by the single, married and then divorced. On the part of teachers who experienced occupational stress at a moderate level, the singles among them had the mean score of 43.33, married had the mean score of 43.69, divorced had the mean score of 37.39 while the widowed had 51.81. Thus, among the teachers with moderate occupational stress level, the widowed had the highest level of job dissatisfaction followed by married, single and then divorced.

Considering the job dissatisfaction of teachers who experience occupational stress at a high level, it is shown that the single among them had a mean score of 43.71. married had 43.66, divorced had 41.63 and the widowed had 54.16. Again, in this high stress level group the widowed had the highest level of dissatisfaction in their jobs, followed by the single, married and then the divorced.

Hypothesis Three: Occupational stress does not significantly influence teachers' job dissatisfaction based on their marital status.

Table 4: Summary of two-way analysis of variance on the influence of occupational stress on teachers' job dissatisfaction based on their marital status

Source of Variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean	F	P-value
Stress Level	3005.71	2	1502.85	12.53	0.000
Marital Status	4260.78	3	1420.26	11.84	0.000
Stress Level x marital status	2735.92	6	455.99	3.80	0.001
Error	44.24.34	367	119.96		
Total	54383.76	378			

From Table 4, it is revealed that the f-value obtained for stress level is 12.53 at df of 2 and 367 at 0.000 level of significance ($P < 0.05$). This indicated a significant influence of stress level on job dissatisfaction among teachers. It is also shown in the same Table 4.8, that the f-value obtained for marital status is 11.84 at df of 3 and 367 at 0.000 level of significance ($P < 0.05$). Thus, the interaction of stress level and marital status significantly influence job dissatisfaction among teachers.

Nevertheless, since marital status had a significant influence on teachers' job dissatisfaction there is need to determine the direction of the significant influence. To job because marital status exists in more than two levels. This was done by subjecting the mean differences to post Hoc multiple comparisons via Schaefer Test. The results obtained are presented in table 5.

Table 5: Determination of direction of significant difference in the influence of marital status on teachers' job dissatisfaction using Schaefer test of multiple comparison

Compared groups	Absolute mean diff	P-value
Single and married	0.0438	1.000
Single and divorced	2.08	0.789
Single and Widowed	10.45	0.000
Married and divorced	2.30	0.700
Married and widowed	10.50	0.000
Divorced and widowed	12.53	0.000

A look at Table 5 above, revealed that the comparison between the following groups (1. single and married teachers 2. single and widowed teachers 3. Married and divorced teachers) means were not significant.

Hence the significant influence/difference of marital status on job dissatisfaction did not result to the comparison between the paired groups mean scores. On the other hand, when the

following group mean scores were compared a significant mean difference resulted. These aspired groups the mean is: Single and widowed, married and widowed and then divorced and widowed

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A finding from the study is that gender significantly influences job dissatisfaction among teachers. This is because across the different occupational stress levels the male teachers had higher mean scores than their female counterparts. This finding is attributed to the fact that most of the males are married and have families to care for following the belief that husbands are the bread winners of their homes. So, the male teacher may be dissatisfied with the job when their salaries are not promptly paid. Again, this finding is attributed to lack of interest on the side of male teachers. This is because most of them in recent times feel that teaching is a job for females and this has reduced the number of male entrants into teaching as a profession. Hence, those currently in the job are just there without interest so any little negative feedback from the government or any other angle may trigger their levels of dissatisfaction in the job.

This finding is not in line with that of Chaplain (1995) who found that gender significantly influence the level of stress experienced by individuals. This disparity in the previous study and the present one is in relation to the variables under study The previous study of Chaplain (1995) focused on gender and stress while this study addressed the issue of gender and job dissatisfaction. However, the two findings have positive relationship due to the fact that they both found that the higher the stress level, the higher the level of job dissatisfaction. That means the previous finding by chaplain that the male teachers experience higher level of stress than their female counterparts imply that the job dissatisfaction level of the male teachers is higher than that of the females.

Furthermore, it was also found that marital status significantly influenced dissatisfaction in job of teachers. Specifically using post. Hoc multiple comparison via Scheffe's Test it was discovered that the comparison between single teachers' mean score and that of the widowed, married teachers' mean score and that of the widowed, divorced teachers, mean score and that of widowed were significantly different. These findings are not surprising but expected because judging from their mean scores irrespective of the stress level, it indicated that the widowed had the highest level of dissatisfaction followed by the single, married and then divorced. These could be attributed to the mismatch between needs and the available resources to satisfy the needs This means that because the widowed had overnight turned to single parents, the trauma of the situation at hand could have triggered the level of dissatisfaction they are facing in the job.

Turning to the single, their level of dissatisfaction may be to some extent similar to the widowed because the trauma of not being married till now, could generate psychological pressures affect their working conditions. To the married it could be that the level of the family responsibility and the remuneration from the working place are not in congruence leading to dissatisfaction in their job. This finding could also be enabled by the social relationships that exist among teachers within the same school environment. This is because some teachers relate well with others while some others are isolated from their colleagues. This finding is does not support that of Njoku (1996) when found that age, sex and years of experience are determinants of stress levels in

teachers. The differences between the two findings depend on the dependent and independent variables. For instance, the previous study was based on the influence of sex as well as age on stress levels of teacher, while the present study focused on marital status and the dissatisfaction level of teachers in their job.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that occupational stress level enhances teachers' job dissatisfaction. This means that secondary school teachers are not satisfied with work due to the high level of stress that has resulted into physiological and psychological strain of their body system. This has resulted in demotivation and lesser passion for their job. In addition, the result showed that on the basis of gender, male teachers reported a higher level of stress than female teachers, while on the basis of marital status, widowed teachers reported the highest level of occupational stress and job dissatisfaction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

First, a proactive measure needs to be taken by the secondary schools board and government hire professional counsellors, sociologist and psychologist whose duty is to give orientation to newly employed staff; and engage in the annual organisation of seminars, trainings or forum on how to handle stress in the workplace and job dissatisfaction.

Second, teachers should be helped to map out strategies to with stressors resulting from the students' behavioural problems and working environment and this should be done by professional industrialists.

Third, government and non-government secondary schools should endeavour to pay salaries promptly, create conducive working environments for employees and ensure timely, consistent appraisal as well as promotions due to employees. They should also take into cognizance the sources of teachers' stress resulting from their attitudes towards work.

REFERENCES

- Adesoji, F. A. (2004). An analysis of occupational stress among science teachers in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical and Counselling Psychology*, 10 (1), 17-28.
- Chaplain, R. (1995). Stress and job satisfaction: A study of English primary school teachers. *Educational Psychology*, 15, 473-490.
- Cooper, C. L. and Dewe, P. (2004). *Stress. A Brief History*. Oxford Blackwell Publishing
- Devereux, J., Hastings, R., & Noone, S. (2009). Staff Stress and Burnout in Intellectual Disability Services: Work Stress Theory and its Application. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 22, 561-573.

- Galanakis, M. Stalikas A, Kallia, H., Karagianni, C., & Karela, C., (2009). Gender differences in experiencing occupational stress the role of age, education and marital status. *Stress and Health*, 25(5), 397-404
- Hannigan, B, Edwards, D, Burnard, P. (2004) Stress and stress management in clinical psychology. Findings from a systematic review. *Journal of Mental Health*, 13. 235-245
- Hornby, A. S. (2010). Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary Ismaili, A. Yan, A & Yunus, N.K.Y (2009) Relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction, An empirical study Malaysia *The Romanian Economic Journal*, 34, 3-29.
- Karasek, R., & Theorell, T. (1990) *Healthy Work Stress, Productivity and the Reconstruction of Working Life*. New York: Basic Books
- Klassen, & Chiu, M.M. (2010). Effects on teacher's self-efficacy and job satisfaction; Teacher gender, years of experience, and stress. *Journal of Education Psychology*, 102, 741-756.
- Kyriacou, C. (2001). Teacher Stress: Directions for future Research. *Education Review*, 53. 27-35
- Landy, FJ. & Conte, J.M. (2004). *Work in 21st Century: An introduction to individual & organizational psychology*. New York: Mc Graw Hill.
- Lazarus R.S. (1995). Psychological stress in the workplace. In R. Crandall. & P.L Perrewe (Eds.), *Occupational Stress A Handbook* (pp 3-15). Washington: Taylor and Francis
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, Coping and Adaptation*. New York Springer
- Leka, S Griffiths, A. and Cox, T (2004) Work organization & stress, systematic problem approaches for employers, managers and trade union representatives. Available at <http://www.int/occupational health/public ations/pwh pdf>. Retrieved on 5 June 2016
- Liu, X. S. and Ramsey, J. (2004) Teachers job satisfaction: Analyses of the teacher follow-up survey in the United States for 2000-2001. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 24, 1173-1184.
- Meshane, S.L. & Glinow, M.A. (2000): *Organizational behaviour*. McGraw Hill Education Publishers

- Moser K. (1997). Commitment in organizations. *Psychologies*, 41(4) 160-170, Okeke, C. (2008). An Empirical Study of Stressors that Impinge on Teachers in Secondary School in Swaziland. *South African Journal of Education*, 33, 32-43. Organ, D.W & Bateman, T.S, (1991). *Organizational behaviour*. Homewood, IRWIN Publishers, p. 291.
- Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (2005). 7th ed. Oxford University Press. Rohany, N. (2003). *A Preliminary study on occupational stress and job satisfaction among male navy personnel*: Utusan Publication Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.
- Salami, S.O. (2005). Management of stress among trainee-teachers through cognitive behavioural therapy. *Personality Study and Group Behaviour*, 26, 1-25.
- Salami, Salim, Arip, & Mustafa, M.B. (2012). *The role of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction among school teachers. The Social Science*. 7. 125-129. Siegel, L. & Lane, L. M. (1982) *Personnel and organizational psychology*. Homewood III: Richard D. Irwin, Inc.
- Spielberger, CD, Vagg, P.R., & Wasala, C.F. (2001) Health psychology and work stress: a more positive approach. In LE. Tetrick, & IC Qusk (Eds.) *Handbook of Occupational* (pp. Psychological Association. 185-200) Washington American
- Tsutsumi, A., Nagami, M., Yoshikawa, T., Kog, K., Kawakawi, N. (2009), Participatory for workplace improvements on mental health and job performance among blue-collar workers, a randomized controlled trial *JOEM*. Volume 51.